

Challenges of Infant Pulmonary Drug Delivery: Aerosol Deposition During Realistic Breathing

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Abstract

Effective inhalation therapy in infants presents significant challenges owing to their distinctive airway anatomy, respiratory patterns, and behavioral factors. This study examined aerosol deposition in a realistic infant airway model under various respiratory conditions, including normal breathing and crying. The airway geometry of a 10-month-old infant was reconstructed from computed tomography scans, and both computational (*in silico*) and experimental (*in vitro*) methodologies were employed to analyze aerosol deposition patterns.

The findings demonstrated that, while a substantial proportion of nebulized aerosol particles (70 %) bypassed the upper respiratory tract during stationary inspiration, realistic breathing patterns revealed considerable variations in deposition. Notably, crying significantly increased aerosol deposition in the upper airways. Particle size also exhibited a crucial role, with 5 μm particles demonstrating 50 % deposition in the upper airways during normal breathing compared to only 6 % for 2.5 μm particles. This observation underscores the suboptimal nature of current inhalation products, which are frequently designed for particle sizes of 1-5 μm .

This study provides valuable insights into aerosol delivery in infants, emphasizing the need for age-specific inhalation therapy. Modifications in particle size distribution, potentially towards smaller particles (1-2.5 μm), may enhance therapeutic outcomes. Further research is warranted to develop infant-specific airway models and to explore alternative particle designs to optimize inhalation drug delivery in this vulnerable population.

Keywords

infant, airways, inhalation, aerosol deposition, computational fluid dynamics.

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1 Introduction

Respiratory illnesses are a common cause of hospitalization in infants, and inhaled medications play a crucial role in their treatment. However, effectively administering these drugs to infants is challenging due to various anatomical, physiological, and behavioral factors. Studies have shown that aerosol drug delivery devices are less efficient in infants (Carrigy et al., 2014; Golshahi et al., 2012; Golshahi, Telidetzki, et al., 2013). Yet, there is a scarcity of research on aerosol deposition using lifelike breathing patterns. This investigation aims to fill this knowledge gap by employing a realistic infant airway model reconstructed from medical imaging data and incorporating actual infant breathing patterns during normal respiration and crying. The goal is to provide a more thorough understanding of aerosol deposition in infants under different breathing conditions, ultimately contributing to the development of more effective, age-appropriate inhalation therapies.

Compared to adults, infants have smaller airways with unique morphological features, leading to increased deposition in the nose, mouth, and throat, and reduced drug delivery to the lungs (Amirav et al., 2012; Amirav & Newhouse, 2012; Golshahi et al., 2012; Golshahi, Vehring, et al., 2013). This difference becomes more pronounced with larger particle sizes and higher flow rates (Amirav et al., 2012). Both experimental and computational studies have confirmed the difficulties of aerosol delivery in infants and emphasized that adult deposition data cannot be simply scaled down for pediatric patients (Golshahi et al., 2012; Golshahi, Vehring, et al., 2013). While some anatomical models for infants exist (e.g., SAINT, prINT) (Janssens et al., 2001; Minocchieri et al., 2008), they often fail to capture the full complexity of the respiratory system (Golshahi et al., 2022). For instance, Xi et al. (Xi et al., 2014) used realistic nasal-laryngeal models but limited their study to stationary inspiration flow rates and excluded the lower airways. In contrast, this study utilizes a realistic airway geometry of a 10-month-old infant, encompassing the nasal cavity, larynx, trachea, and two generations of bronchial branching. Importantly, simulations were conducted not only for steady

inhalation but also for realistic tidal breathing, including both normal and crying modes. These recordings of normal breathing and crying are uncommon or nonexistent in the literature, making the data presented here a unique and valuable contribution to the field.

1.1 Challenges of aerosol delivery in infants

Aerosol delivery in infants faces obstacles beyond the anatomical issues. Behavioral and technical aspects significantly impact treatment effectiveness. While adults can typically master inhalation methods and use inhalers effectively, studies using radiolabeled aerosols have shown that inhaled drug delivery is more successful in older individuals compared to younger ones (Roller et al., 2006; Schuepp et al., 2009; Tal et al., 1996; Wildhaber et al., 1999, 2000). Children often experience reduced deposition due to mask leakage, crying, or inability to follow inhalation instructions (Carrigy et al., 2014). To establish safe and effective treatments, physicians often rely on empirical experience outside the labeled limits of the drug (Fink, 2012). The choice of inhalation device and interface is crucial and age dependent. Inhalers are not designed for pediatric use, and only child-sized masks are used to facilitate drug administration (Fink, 2012).

Additionally, non-compliance of pediatric patients with inhalation therapy poses a significant challenge. A study by Iles et al. (Iles et al., 1999) examined how crying during inhalation affects pulmonary drug delivery. Although the research could not identify differences in regional aerosol deposition during crying, it conclusively demonstrated that crying substantially reduced the efficiency of aerosol delivery to the lungs (Iles et al., 1999). The results of that study indicate that infant cooperation is vital for successful treatment.

Various solutions have been proposed to address these challenges, with varying degrees of effectiveness. One method involves utilizing a nebulization hood positioned around the patient's head, into which the medicinal aerosol is released (Amirav, 2003; Kim et al., 2014). This technique

eliminates the need to cause distress to the patient by placing an inhalation mask on the face. A study by Amirav et al. (2003) compared the drug delivery efficiency between this chamber approach and the conventional method of applying a mask to the mouth and nose in 14 children aged 1–19 months. The administered medication was labeled with technetium-99m, enabling the assessment of aerosol deposition locations. The research concluded that the chamber was equally effective as traditional mask inhalation in terms of lung deposition fraction and clinical response. Notably, the inter-subject variability in deposition was higher with mask usage. The conventional approach also presents difficulties in maintaining a secure mask seal on a child's face for extended periods. As a result, parents gave highly positive ratings to the nebulization chamber (Amirav, 2003). A significant drawback of this solution is the potential for contamination of the face and eyes, as the medication is dispersed throughout the chamber volume surrounding the face (Kim et al., 2014). Factors such as facial position and orientation, along with breathing patterns, significantly impact this contamination, which cannot be completely eliminated (Kim et al., 2014).

An alternative method to soothe children during inhalation therapy involves incorporating a pacifier into the inhalation mask. This approach allows the child to suck on the pacifier while inhaling, potentially resulting in a more relaxed treatment experience. Amirav et al. (Amirav et al., 2012) evaluated this concept using a similar methodology to the previously discussed study, employing nebulized aerosol tagged with technetium-99m. While the regional deposition efficiency was comparable to that of a standard inhalation mask, a notable difference was observed in patients' acceptance of the treatment (Amirav et al., 2012). Like the nebulization chamber, this technique did not significantly enhance the proportion of aerosol deposited in the lungs. Nevertheless, it improved patient cooperation, which can be crucial for parents administering the treatment. Although crying subjects showed increased aerosol deposition in the upper respiratory tract, this difference was not statistically significant due to result variability. Moreover, unlike the nebulization chamber, this method prevents the patient's face from being exposed to therapeutic contamination.

A third strategy to enhance child compliance with inhalation therapy focuses on distracting the child. Frémont et al. (Frémont et al., 2018) investigated this approach at the University Hospital in Paris. The study involved 11 asthmatic children aged between one month and five years. These patients received inhalation therapy through a spacer with an inhalation mask. A smartphone was attached to the inhaler, positioning its screen directly in the patient's field of vision. During treatment, periods without screen activity were alternated with periods of animated cartoon playback. The cartoon viewing significantly improved treatment cooperation among the studied patient group (Frémont et al., 2018).

However, these approaches primarily aim to influence patient behavior. While enhancing cooperation is important, it may not be sufficient to optimize aerosol delivery. As these studies indicate, even with improved compliance, the inherent limitations of existing inhalation devices and aerosol formulations may impede effective drug delivery to the lungs. This underscores the necessity for a more comprehensive understanding of aerosol deposition patterns in infants under realistic breathing conditions. The present study addresses this need by utilizing a realistic airway replica of a 10-month-old child and incorporating actual breathing patterns, including crying, to inform the design of more effective inhalation products for infants.

2 Materials and Methods

This chapter describes the methods used to construct the infant airway geometry, validate the computational model, and simulate aerosol deposition under realistic breathing conditions.

2.1 Processing of the medical imaging data

The infant airway geometry was created by combining scans from two 10-month-old subjects. The upper airway part was based on Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) data, while the tracheobronchial (TB) part was based on X-ray Computed Tomography (X-ray CT) data. This combination was necessary due to the limited availability of datasets containing both upper and lower airways from a single imaging modality for infants of this age. Ethical considerations restricted us to using only datasets obtained for clinically indicated reasons, and no single, comprehensive scan was available. Dimensional compatibility between the two datasets was ensured by selecting geometries with identical tracheal diameters, minimizing the potential for discontinuities at the junction.

The process of creating the digital airway geometry involved the following steps:

1. **Registration and Cropping:** Initially, both the MRI and CT datasets were registered into a common coordinate system using anatomical landmarks. This ensured that the two scans were spatially aligned. Following registration, the datasets were cropped to include only the region of interest, namely the airways and a small portion of the surrounding tissues, to reduce the computational load in subsequent steps.
2. **Resampling:** To unify the datasets and minimize voxel-based artifacts (the "stair-step" effect), both datasets were resampled to a voxel size of 0.2 mm. This isotropic resolution was chosen to balance the need for accurate geometric representation with computational efficiency.
3. **Filtering:** A bilateral filter with a kernel size of 5 voxels and a standard deviation of 3 was applied to both datasets. This nonlinear filter effectively smoothed the data while preserving important edge information. It reduced noise and small-scale artifacts, enhancing the definition of airway boundaries for the subsequent segmentation process. The bilateral filter can be expressed as:

$$BF(I)_p = \frac{1}{W_p} G_{\sigma_s} (\| p - q \|) G_{\sigma_r} (I_p - I_q) I_q, \quad (1)$$

where W_p is a normalisation factor, G_{σ_s} is a spatial Gaussian function that decreases the influence of distant pixels. G_{σ_r} is a range Gaussian function that decreases the influence of pixels with different intensities, q represents neighboring pixels within the kernel, p is a central pixel.

4. **Segmentation:** A custom-written region-growing algorithm implemented in Matlab was employed to segment the internal air volume of the airways from the surrounding tissues. This algorithm iteratively adds neighboring voxels to a starting "seed" region based on intensity similarity. The intensity threshold for adding a voxel was dynamically computed as the mean intensity of its 26-connected neighborhood. This adaptive thresholding helped to account for local variations in image intensity. In the nasopharynx region, where the air-tissue contrast was particularly low and the airway passages were narrow, manual adjustments to the segmentation were necessary to ensure accuracy.
5. **Alignment and Connection:** The final step involved connecting the segmented upper airway (from MRI) and TB airway (from CT) datasets. This was performed in Avizo software (Thermo Fisher Scientific) using manual alignment based on anatomical landmarks. The overlapping portion of the trachea, present in both datasets, was preserved from the CT dataset due to the higher contrast and better segmentation quality in that region.

The resulting airway geometry was then supplemented with a mask placed in front of the nasal replica, mimicking the shape of a mask used in inhalation therapy. The airway geometry was segmented into four regions (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: The airway replica of a 10-month-old infant with visualized segments.

2.2 Boundary conditions and experimentally acquired validation data

2.2.1 Aerodynamic particle size distribution

The aerodynamic particle size distribution of the aerosol generated by the Aerogen Solo nebulizer was measured using an Andersen cascade impactor (ACI). This nebulizer was chosen due to its common use in infants and its ability to generate aerosols with a suitable particle size distribution for inhalation therapy. Fluorescein sodium salt was used as the tracer substance due to its ease of detection and its well-established use in aerosol deposition studies.

To prevent evaporation of the liquid particles during the experiment, the ACI was cooled to 5°C in a refrigerator, as recommended by the European Pharmacopoeia (Ph. Eur.) (Council of Europe et al., 2005). Once the impactor reached the desired temperature, a solution of fluorescein sodium salt with a concentration of 300 µg/ml was nebulized using the Aerogen Solo nebulizer. The impactor was configured for an inhalation flow rate of 28.3 L/min, the lowest allowed flow rate of the device.

After the exposure, the individual stages of the ACI were rinsed with distilled water, and the concentration of fluorescein deposited in each segment was measured using a Quantus™ Fluorometer (Promega Corp., Wisconsin, USA). The mass fractions deposited on the individual stages were then used to calculate the aerodynamic size distribution, including the mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD), geometric standard deviation (GSD), and fine particle fraction (FPF), according to the method described in (Finlay, 2001). These parameters are shown in Tab. 1. The measured size distribution, which exhibited a large FPF value potentially indicative of high lung deposition, was adopted for the computational modeling. The distribution of aerodynamic particle size is shown in Fig. 2.

Tab. 1: Aerodynamic particle size distribution parameters.

MMAD (μm)	2.20 ± 0.53
GSD (—)	2.50 ± 0.57
FPF (%)	81.25 ± 3.62

Fig. 2: Aerodynamic particle size distribution.

2.2.2 Experimental Measurements of Aerosol Deposition

To validate the computational model, aerosol deposition experiments were conducted using the same 3D-printed infant airway replica (for technical details of the replica production technology see (Prinz et al., 2024)). Each outlet of the lower respiratory tract was equipped with a filter to capture particles capable of penetrating deeper into the lungs. The replica was connected to a vacuum pump (Busch R5 PA0008C, Busch Vacuum Solutions s.r.o Czech Republic) via a distributor, with flow rates through the individual branches set to match those used in the computational model, as specified in Tab. 5.

Aerosol was generated using the Aerogen Solo nebulizer connected to the inlet of the mask via an electroconductive hose. During the experiment, a solution of sodium fluorescein at a concentration of 300 μg/ml was nebulized. To minimize droplet evaporation, the entire experimental setup, including the replica, was cooled to 5°C, consistent with the procedure used for measuring the particle size distribution. The model was placed in a refrigerator, and its surface temperature was monitored using a thermocouple. The measurement setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Exposure of the model to the fluorescently labeled aerosol lasted for 1 minute. Subsequently, the replica was disassembled into its segments (mask, upper airways, trachea, branching, collection filters). The deposited aerosol was extracted from each segment using an ultrasonic cleaner and analyzed using fluorometry. The measured fluorescein concentrations were used to determine the mass of deposited aerosol in each segment. Since the nebulized solution was homogeneous, the fluorescein deposition fractions directly corresponded to the aerosol particle deposition fractions.

Fig. 3: Scheme of *in vitro* aerosol deposition measurement.

2.2.3 Recordings of the realistic breathing patterns

To obtain realistic breathing patterns for use in the computational simulations, the breathing patterns of six infants under one year of age were recorded after obtaining ethical approval (Ethics Committee of FN Brno, number 01-131021/EK) and informed consent from legal guardians. The age and weight of the subjects are listed in Tab. 2.

Tab. 2: Age and weight of the subjects.

	<i>Postnatal age (week)</i>	<i>Weight (kg)</i>
Sub1	48	9.0
Sub2	44	7.9
Sub3	51	11.2
Sub4	52	9.8
Sub5	46	8.3
Sub6	13	6.0

An infant resuscitation mask connected to a SpiroSonic Smart® spirometer was used to record the breathing patterns. The mask was placed on the subject's face without obstructing the nasal airways. Simultaneously, video recordings were made to identify different breathing behaviors, including calm breathing and crying. The crying mode, characterized by braked exhalation, was successfully recorded for three out of the six subjects.

The recorded breathing profiles were divided into normal calm breathing and breathing with a braked exhalation. Braked exhalation accompanies various breathing modes and is also part of crying or whimpering in children (Arjan et al., 2009), henceforth referred to as the crying mode in this work. The division was based on the shape of the braked exhalation described in (Langlois & Baken, 1976). Selected recordings of characteristic shapes of breathing cycles corresponding to the mentioned modes are shown in Fig. 4. Braked exhalation (Fig. 4 – right) causes an extension of the exhalation phase, thereby increasing the need for a more forceful inhalation.

Fig. 4: An example of a breathing profile for normal tidal breathing (left) and crying (right).

After dividing the recorded cycles into crying mode and normal breathing, the average parameters were evaluated from the inhalations: TV (tidal volume), $T_{i, normal}$ (inhalation duration of normal breathing), and $T_{i, cry}$ (inhalation duration during crying).

The flow rate over time was recorded as described above. The recordings were then divided into inhalations and exhalations. Erroneous samples (e.g., fluctuations, coughing, etc.) were removed from the statistical set. The processing of the record is described in the following steps:

1. Separation of the record into inhalations/exhalations (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Separation of breathing recordings into individual inspirations and expirations.

2. **Normalization of the inhalation/expiration profiles for the studied regime.** To avoid the effects of individual characteristics such as age, lung volume, and natural breathing frequency, the flow values at each time step t_i^* were normalised by the average inhalation flow rate of the subject obtained during the breathing without a nebuliser. Thus, $\dot{V}_i^* = \frac{\dot{V}_i}{\bar{\dot{V}}_i}$, where, $\bar{\dot{V}}_i = \frac{\overline{TV}}{\bar{T}_i}$, where \dot{V}_i^* is the normalised flow rate at a given time step, \dot{V}_i is the recorded flow rate at a given time step, $\bar{\dot{V}}_i$ is the average inhalation flow rate of the subject, \overline{TV} is the average tidal volume of the subject during spontaneous breathing, and \bar{T}_i is the average inhalation duration of the subject during spontaneous breathing. Each inhalation and expiration was normalised in this way as shown in Fig. 6.

3. Reconstruction of the breathing cycle profile representing the studied mode. Normalising the flow rate in this way is very useful because it allows a reverse reconstruction of the breathing profile for a specific patient, as the parameters \overline{TV} and \overline{T}_i can be easily acquired from the patient's spirometry and used for a very good approximation of the individual breathing profile. Thus the profiles presented here can serve for the modeling of personalised drug delivery to the lungs. The empirical equations of normalized breathing profiles are shown in Fig. 6.

The average breathing parameters (TV_{normal} , $T_{i,normal}$, $T_{i,cry}$) are shown in Tab. 3. The ratio of the inhalation duration during crying to calm breathing is $T_{i,cry}/T_{i,normal} = 0.66 \pm 0.09$.

Tab. 3: Elementary breathing parameters of the recorded subjects.

	TV_{normal} (ml)	$T_{i,normal}$ (s)	$T_{i,cry}$ (s)
SUB1	97.00 ± 25.23	0.54 ± 0.17	—
SUB2	92.78 ± 17.69	0.50 ± 0.18	—
SUB3	98.22 ± 38.02	0.43 ± 0.17	0.25 ± 0.05
SUB4	91.99 ± 22.62	0.66 ± 0.08	0.42 ± 0.04
SUB5	71.33 ± 13.04	0.50 ± 0.09	—
SUB6	31.69 ± 11.20	0.37 ± 0.15	0.28 ± 0.06

Fig. 6: Mean normalized breathing profiles of cry and normal breathing.

The obtained average profiles correspond approximately to a parabolic shape, and significantly less so to a sinusoidal function. Thus, for modeling breathing patterns, utilizing a second-degree polynomial for the shape of the inhalation appears to be more appropriate than a sinusoidal shape. In testing the delivered dose of inhalation products according to the standardized methodology established by Ph. Eur., a sinusoidal pattern is employed to model cyclic breathing for all modeled cases, including children's breathing. Future studies should therefore compare the impact and error of modeling a sinusoidal breathing pattern with respect to the dose delivered to the patient and the regional deposition of the aerosol in the lungs.

The peak inspiratory flow rate during the cry was, according to these data, approximately 1.7 times higher than in the case of normal tidal breathing. Concurrently, the inspiration times during the cry and discomfort were 0.66 times shorter than during normal tidal breathing.

The limitation of this part of the study was primarily the difficulty of collecting data on children's breathing, resulting in a limited statistical sample of breathing records. Not only was it challenging to secure a larger number of subjects in the given age cohort, but the recording process itself was highly complex due to the non-cooperation of the subjects. Regrettably, for some children initially involved in the study, it was not possible to record even a single complete breathing cycle, necessitating their subsequent exclusion from the study.

The representative breathing profiles were reconstructed from the normalized breathing profiles depicted in Fig. 6 by utilizing the mean inspiratory flow rate (8.4 L/min) and the mean duration (0.675 s) of the 10-month-old infant inspiration employed in the steady inspiratory flow rate modeling. These reconstructed breathing profiles, illustrated in Fig. 7, were subsequently utilized as boundary conditions for airway deposition simulations of the realistic breathing profiles.

Fig. 7: Reconstructed breathing profiles used for the *in silico* airway deposition analyses.

2.3 Computational Modeling

2.3.1 General Setup of the Computational Simulations

CFD simulations were conducted utilizing Simcenter Star-CCM+ 17.06.007 (Siemens) software, employing an unstructured mesh composed of polyhedral elements. The narrow channels present in the nasal cavity and tracheobronchial tree necessitated local mesh refinement to ensure adequate resolution and capture the complex flow patterns in these regions. This refinement strategy also served to optimize computational efficiency by avoiding unnecessary refinement in the larger volume of the inlet mask.

A grid independence study was performed using six meshes with varying refinement factors (Tab. 4) to ensure that the simulation results were not influenced by mesh resolution. The average flow velocity at selected points (Fig. 8) was evaluated for each mesh, and the final mesh (No. 2 with refinement by a factor of 0.7) was selected based on the convergence of these velocities (Fig. 9).

Fig. 8: The location of point probes for the mesh independency study

Tab. 4: The parameters of the spatial discretisation for the mesh independency study.

	1	2	3	4	5	6
The factor of the cell refinement (base size)	0.60	0.70	0.80	1.00	1.20	1.40
The factor of local refinement - Nasal cavity	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35
The factor of local refinement – Tracheobronchial area	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52
Cell size - Mask (mm)	0.52	0.61	0.70	0.87	1.04	1.22
Cell size - Nasal cavity (mm)	0.18	0.21	0.24	0.30	0.37	0.43
Cell size - Tracheobronchial area (mm)	0.27	0.32	0.36	0.45	0.54	0.63
Total cell number (mil)	5.99	4.37	3.75	3.24	2.82	2.57

Fig. 9: Velocity magnitude comparison in observed point probes for the mesh independency study.

An unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) approach was employed to solve the flow field. This methodology is appropriate for capturing the transient flow behavior associated with realistic breathing patterns. The Menter SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model was utilized to model turbulent behavior. This model provides an optimal balance of accuracy and computational efficiency for internal flows. A segregated solver with the SIMPLE algorithm was implemented for pressure-velocity coupling. This approach is frequently utilized for incompressible flows. Second-order upwind differencing was applied for spatial discretization to ensure numerical accuracy. The time step was adaptively adjusted to satisfy the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) condition, thereby ensuring numerical stability.

Velocity boundary conditions were applied at the bronchial outlets, with the outward-pointing velocity profile defined according to the recorded breathing patterns. A pressure boundary condition with atmospheric pressure was established at the inlet of the mask.

A Lagrangian approach was employed to model the transport of aerosol particles within the domain, with 100 evenly distributed points created 1 mm from the mask inlet (Fig. 10) serving as particle injection sites.

Fig. 10: Point injectors distribution.

The motion of each particle was determined by solving the following force balance equation:

$$m_p \frac{dv_p}{dt} = F_s + F_b, \quad (2)$$

where F_s represents the sum of the forces acting on the particle's surface, m_p is the particle mass, v_p is the particle velocity, t is time, and F_b are body forces. In this case,

$$F_s = F_d + F_p, \quad (3)$$

where F_p is the force due to the pressure gradient and F_d is the drag force given by:

$$F_d = \frac{1}{2} C_d \rho A_p |v_s| v_s, \quad (4)$$

where C_d is the particle drag coefficient, ρ is the density of the carrier medium, A_p is the projected area of the particle, and v_s is the slip velocity, defined as $v_s = v - v_p$ (where v is the instantaneous velocity of the carrier medium). The drag coefficient C_d was determined using the Schiller-Neumann correlation:

$$C_d = \begin{cases} \frac{24}{Re_p} (1 + 0,15 Re_p^{0,687}) & Re_p \leq 10^3 \\ 0,44 & Re_p > 10^3 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where Re_p is the particle Reynolds number defined as:

$$Re_p = \frac{\rho |v_s| d_p}{\mu}, \quad (6)$$

with d_p being the particle diameter and μ the air dynamic viscosity. The force due to the pressure gradient F_p was calculated as:

$$F_p = -V_p \nabla p_{static}, \quad (7)$$

where V_p is the particle volume and ∇p_{static} is the gradient of the static pressure. Of the body forces, only gravity was considered.

Since the RANS approach smooths out flow fluctuations due to averaging, the turbulent dispersion model was applied to correctly simulate the particle movement. Particle deposition was modeled using the "Boundary Sampling" model, with particles considered deposited upon contact with the airway walls (the "Stick" condition).

Particles were injected into the domain with a time step of 0.001 s for a duration of 0.2 s. A total of 600,000 particles were injected, with their sizes distributed according to the measured particle size distribution. This allowed for direct comparison between the simulation results and the experimental measurements. After the initial injection period, an additional 1 s of physical time was simulated to ensure that most particles had interacted with the airway walls.

2.3.2 Model Validation

Before simulating realistic breathing regimes, the computational model was validated using experimental measurements of aerosol deposition during steady inspiration. The breathing parameters for a 10-month-old infant were obtained from the literature: tidal volume (TV) of 0.095 L, respiratory rate (RR) of 37.33 breaths per minute, inspiration-expiration (IE) ratio of 0.42, and inspiration time (T_i) of 0.675 s (Dizdar et al., 2020; Doershuk et al., 1970; Fleming et al., 2011; Hmeidi et al., 2017; Roi & Courta, 1991). These values resulted in an average inspiratory flow rate of 8.4 L/min.

To ensure realistic airflow distribution in the respiratory tract, data from dynamic CT recordings of adult breathing were used (Jahani et al., 2015). This was necessary due to the lack of similar data for infants. The adult data were averaged over time to obtain a representative distribution for the stationary inspiration condition. The resulting distribution is shown in Tab. 5.

Tab. 5: Lobar distribution of flow rate. RU - Right upper; RL – Right Lower; RM – Right middle; LU – Left upper; LL – Left lower.

	Flow rate (l/min)
<i>Total</i>	8.40
<i>RU</i>	1.76
<i>RL+RM</i>	2.79
<i>LU</i>	2.13
<i>LL</i>	1.73

2.3.3 Realistic Breathing Simulations

This section describes the computational simulations performed using the realistic breathing patterns recorded in Section 2.2.3.

In the realistic breathing simulations, the inhalation mask was removed from the computational domain (see Fig. 11). This was necessary because the presence of the mask would have introduced an artificial delay in the aerosol transport, as the aerosol would need to first pass through the mask volume before entering the respiratory tract. By removing the mask, the simulations more accurately reflect the actual timing of aerosol inhalation.

An unstructured mesh with polyhedral elements was created, similar to the meshing strategy used in the validation case. Local refinement was applied in the nasal cavity and tracheobronchial tree to ensure adequate resolution in these critical areas, where complex flow patterns are expected. An unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) approach with the Menter SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model was used again to solve the flow field.

Fig. 11: Model of the infant airways after removing the inhalation mask.

A Lagrangian approach was employed to model the transport of aerosol particles, considering drag force, gravity, and turbulent dispersion. In contrast to the stationary flow case, particles were emitted from injectors created in each nostril. These injectors functioned as point sources distributed across the nostril inlets (Fig. 12). To prevent particle entrapment in low-velocity regions near the nostril walls, the prismatic boundary layer cells were removed from the injector planes. Due to the disparity in cell numbers between the injector planes in the two nostrils, different probabilities were assigned to the injector points to ensure an equal number of particles entered through each nostril.

Particles were injected into the domain throughout the entire duration of inhalation. The time step for particle injection was set independently of the adaptive computation time step. For normal breathing, the injection time step was 0.00473 s with an inhalation duration of 0.675 s. For crying, the corresponding times were 0.003104 s and 0.443 s, respectively. The probability of injector point engagement was set so that 350 points from each nostril participated in the injection during each time step. Each point injected 5 parcels into the domain at each injection moment, with each parcel representing one particle. Consequently, a total of 500,000 particles of a single size were injected into the domain through both nostrils over the entire inhalation period. Injectors were configured in this manner for particle sizes of 1 μm , 2.5 μm , and 5 μm .

Fig. 12: The particle injector in the nostril plane.

2.4 Limitations of the Model

This study has some limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. The geometry used in this study does not include the oral cavity due to limitations in the available medical imaging data. While this omission is not expected to significantly affect the simulations of normal tidal breathing, where infants predominantly breathe through their noses, it may influence the accuracy of simulations for crying episodes, where oral breathing contributes. For this reason, the analysis of the crying mode focused mainly on airways below the glottis.

It must be also noted, that the airway geometry is based on scans from two infants, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader infant population.

Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable insights into aerosol deposition in infants under realistic breathing conditions, highlighting the importance of considering breathing patterns and particle size in the design of inhalation therapies for this age group. Future studies could further refine these findings by incorporating oral airway geometry and utilizing a larger sample size.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Airway Deposition During the Steady Inspiration Flow Rate

Fig. 13 shows a comparison of the computational and experimental results for aerosol deposition in the infant airway replica during steady inspiration at a flow rate of 8.4 L/min. Overall, the computational and experimental results show good agreement in terms of the deposition patterns. The maximum difference of 3.4 % was found in the segment containing the 1st and 2nd airway branching. However, there is some variability observed in the experimental data, particularly in the fraction of aerosol deposited in the upper respiratory tract. This variability could be attributed to several factors,

including variations in nebulizer output, challenges in extracting deposited aerosol from the narrow nasal passages (although the thoroughness of the extraction was ensured by repeated extraction until no fluorescein content was measured after extraction), and inherent uncertainties in the experimental measurements. Despite this variability, the overall agreement between the computational and experimental results supports the validity of the computational model for predicting aerosol deposition in the infant airways.

The results indicate that approximately 70 % of the nebulized aerosol mass is delivered past the upper respiratory tract during steady inspiration using the Aerogen Solo nebulizer. While 70 % might seem like a reasonable fraction, it is essential to consider that this was measured under steady flow conditions, which do not fully represent the dynamic nature of infant breathing. The following section shows the results for aerosol deposition during realistic breathing profiles, which provide a more accurate picture of aerosol behavior in infants.

Fig. 13: In vitro and in silico results of aerosol deposition in the airway replica of the 10-month-old child. The error bars indicate the standard deviations calculated from experiments. The error bars for the trachea and the 1st and 2nd branching are smaller than the thickness of the line.

The portion of aerosol that penetrated below the upper airways was similar to FPF determined by ACI, which may seem that the common criterion for aerosol size of inhalation products is also suitable for infants. However, with realistic cyclic breathing, the deposition distribution may significantly differ, as can be seen in the next section.

3.2 Airway deposition during the realistic breathing profiles

The regional deposition of aerosol particles during normal calm breathing and crying was investigated for three particle sizes: 1 μm , 2.5 μm , and 5 μm . Fractions of all inhaled particles deposited in different regions of the infant airways during realistic breathing conditions are shown in Tab. 6. The results reveal significant differences in deposition patterns between the two breathing modes. It is important to note that the airway geometry used in this study includes only the nasal passage. Therefore, the deposition fractions reported in upper airways for the crying mode (where in reality the oral breathing may contribute), should be considered an upper estimate. While the actual upper airway deposition during crying might be lower when oral inhalation is considered, it is unlikely to be as low as that observed during normal breathing. This is because the nasal route in infants offers lower resistance to airflow compared to adults and consistently carries a significant portion of inhaled air, even during crying.

The simulations also showed a strong dependence of aerosol deposition on particle size. In particular, 51.5 % of the inhaled 5 μm particles were deposited in the upper airways during normal tidal breathing through the nasal route, compared to only 5.9 % of 2.5 μm particles and 2.1 % of 1 μm particles. This indicates that even a small change in particle size within the range typically found in inhalation products can significantly affect upper airway deposition in infants.

Tab. 6: Fractions of all inhaled particles deposited in different regions of the infant airways during normal breathing and crying.

	Fractions of inhaled particles [%]					
	Normal breathing			Crying		
	1 μm	2.5 μm	5 μm	1 μm	2.5 μm	5 μm
Upper airways	2.1 %	5.9 %	51.5 %	4.1 %	24.6 %	83.1 %
Trachea	3.1 %	5.8 %	7.1 %	9.9 %	13.0 %	4.2 %
1st bifurcation	1.6 %	1.9 %	2.0 %	3.4 %	3.4 %	1.2 %
2nd bifurcation	2.5 %	3.4 %	5.8 %	6.2 %	6.6 %	3.1 %
Lower airways	90.8 %	83.1 %	33.6 %	76.3 %	52.4 %	8.5 %

The fractions of deposited particles in segments from the trachea to the second generation of airway branching are shown in Fig. 14. The fractions there are calculated from the total amount of particles entering the trachea to avoid the influence of the missing oral airways (in contrast to Tab. 6 where fractions of all inhaled particles are presented). The deposition in the trachea and the first two branching generations is much more significant during crying than during normal breathing. In crying, the percentage of particles penetrating below the 2nd generation of branching dropped by 19.3 %, 18.7 %, and 13.3 % in the case of 5 μm , 2.5 μm , and 1 μm particles, respectively, compared to normal tidal breathing.

The 2.5 μm particles were more capable of penetrating the whole replica. The fraction of such particles from the total number of particles that entered the trachea was 69.6 % during crying and 88.3% during normal tidal breathing, while in the case of 5 μm particles, this fraction was 50 % when crying and 69.3% when breathing normally. In the case of 1 μm particles, 92.4 % of particles that entered the trachea penetrated below the second generation when breathing normally, and 79.5 % did so when crying.

This data shows how challenging it is to deliver the inhalation drug deeper into the infant's airways and suggests the optimal size range for such delivery. This also indicates that crying during inhalation significantly affects the deposition not only in the extrathoracic region but also in the tracheobronchial area by enhancing the deposition in the first branching generations. Inhalation products are designed to contain predominately particles from 1 to 5 μm (Hickey, 2019). Yet, just shifting the size from 5 μm to 2.5 μm enlarged the portion of particles that got deeper into the airways by 20 % in both breathing regimes, which suggests designing the aerosol particles to be smaller (ideally in the range of 1-2.5 μm) for inhalation treatment of infants. A possible and promising way of overcoming this obstacle could be by inhaling particles with design shapes, such as fiber or rod particles (Farkas et al., 2019; Lizal et al., 2022). It must be noted that, due to the size-dependent deposition mechanisms, particles smaller than 1 μm could easily be exhaled from the respiratory tract, or, in the case of very small particles (<0.3 μm), effectively deposited in the upper respiratory tract due to diffusion (Hinds, 1999).

Fig. 14: Aerosol deposition fraction in a 10-month-old child tracheobronchial area of the airway replica during the realistic breathing modes.

4 Conclusions

This study demonstrates the critical impact of breathing patterns and particle size on aerosol deposition in infants. Realistic simulations of normal breathing and crying revealed significant differences in deposition patterns, highlighting the need for age-specific considerations in the design of inhalation therapies.

The findings indicate that crying significantly alters airflow patterns in infants, with inhalation flow rates nearly double those observed during normal breathing. This leads to increased deposition in the upper airways and tracheobronchial region compared to normal breathing, particularly for larger particles. This underscores the importance of considering the influence of crying and other distress behaviors on aerosol delivery in infants. The recordings of breathing patterns presented in this study can be utilized for patient-specific modeling of other subjects, provided the TV and T_i are known from spirometry.

Furthermore, the results demonstrate that the particle size range typically found in adult inhalation products (1-5 μm) is suboptimal for infants. In other words, simply adapting adult nebulizers for infants by using smaller face masks is an inadequate drug delivery strategy. Even during normal breathing, a small change in particle size within this range can significantly affect deposition. For instance, while 5 μm particles exhibited approximately 50% deposition in the upper airways during normal breathing, 2.5 μm particles exhibited only approximately 6%. To enhance drug delivery to the lungs, it is crucial to design inhalation therapies with smaller particle sizes, ideally in the range of 1-2.5 μm , for infants.

This study was limited by the use of subject-specific airway geometries and the exclusion of the oral cavity. Future research should prioritize the development of infant-specific airway models that are representative of a larger portion of the infant population. Further investigations are necessary to fully characterize aerosol deposition during crying episodes, which may involve oral breathing and require a more comprehensive airway model. Additionally, further research into the impact of different breathing patterns on aerosol deposition using a wider range of particle sizes and shapes, such as fibers or rods, is warranted.

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6 CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ondrej Mišík: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualisation; **František Prinz:** Formal analysis, Software, Data Curation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Jakub Elcner:** Supervision, Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Jakub Lazňovský:** Methodology, Writing – Review & Editing; **Miloslav Bělka:** Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Tomáš Juren:** Supervision, Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Jan Jedelsky:** Writing – Review & Editing. **František Lízal:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Writing – Review & Editing.

7 Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

8 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors utilized the assistance of an AI language model Gemini (Google Inc.) for correcting and revising the language and grammar. After using this tool, the authors carefully reviewed and edited the content, taking full responsibility for the final version of the manuscript.

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